

Designing Control Systems with Empirical Logic

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Abstract. Empirical logic is a bionic-inspired method of soft computing that deliberately does not link to mathematical logic or fuzzy logic. Rather, it mimics a natural reasoning mechanism that resides in the human subconscious and is referred to in psychology as System 1. The example of speed control of a DC drive shows the basic procedure for using empirical logic in control engineering. Compared to similar fuzzy control solutions, empirical logic control exhibits even better dynamic behavior and accuracy with significantly lower development effort.

Keywords: Control engineering, Empirical logic, Soft computing, Approximate reasoning, Bio-inspired computing, Nature inspired computing

1 Introduction

Empirical logic is an innovative rule-based soft computing method for decision-making with expert knowledge [1]. For a detailed description, see the doctoral thesis of the author [2]. As a formal language, its development goes back to a bionic approach, in which the functioning of the subconscious known in psychology and neuroscience as *System 1* was chosen as a model [3]. System 1 represents the innate ability of the human brain to instinctively categorize any type of perception by automatically associating it to vital emotional reactions (e.g., fear) and memorized experiences. As early as 1987, David D. Tank and John J. Hopfield [4] published results from experiments with neuronlike electronic circuits which support the assumption that the collective excitation propagation of System 1 bears a structural resemblance to the functioning of the biological neural network that performs it [5] [6]. With the help of the Maple computer algebra system [7, p. 998 ff.], the author has built a prototype of an empirical logic program library and tested it using several practical application examples from business administration, economics, operations research and control engineering [8]. In particular, the control engineering examples have shown that, in comparison to corresponding fuzzy control system solutions, they exhibit better dynamic behavior and accuracy with significantly lower development effort. For illustration purposes, this paper will describe how a speed control system for a DC drive was implemented with empirical logic.

2 Some principles of Empirical Logic (EL)

The following remarks serve to recall the foundations of empirical logic as presented in “*Thinking fast: a bionic approach to soft computing*” [1], which prior reading is strongly recommended.

The basic mechanism of a nervous system consists in the directed point-to-point transmission of signals of different intensity between nerve cells or *neurons*. The contact points between the nerve cells, known as *synapses*, play a key role because they determine whether the activity of the signal-receiving nerve cell is *excited* or *inhibited*.

This signal communication principle is also reflected in the basic concepts of empirical logic:

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1. Notions that we use to mentally organize the information we perceive from our environment, such as facts, individuals, observed characteristics, actions, decisions, etc., are abstracted by empirical logic into the concept of *category*. Analogously to the excitation state of a neuron, a category has a dynamic state called *validity* that is usually measured on a sliding scale \mathbb{V} between +1 and -1, such that +1 (-1) corresponds to the meaning “The fact does (not) belong to this category”. *Bound (free) categories* are (not) bound to a scalable reference magnitude. The empirical logic method distinguishes four standardized validity functions to characterize a bound category:

- Threshold function ($e_THRESHOLD$)
- Limitation function ($e_LIMITATION$)
- Interval function ($e_INTERVAL$)
- Estimation function ($e_ESTIMATION$)

For each of these validity functions, there is also a corresponding inverse function defined (e.g. $e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE$).

2. The *paradigm of circumstantial evidence* forms the semantic basis model of empirical logic, where both *pro-* or *contra-indications* and *hypotheses* are represented by categories.
3. Asserting a category validity (e.g. approving a hypothesis) is represented by the $e_VALIDATE$ operator and corresponds to an *excitatory synapse*.
4. Refuting a category validity (e.g. disproving a hypothesis) is represented by the $e_INVALIDATE$ operator and corresponds to an *inhibitory synapse*.

3 Speed control of a DC drive using empirical logic (application example)

The following example of the speed control of a DC drive is taken from a well-known textbook on control engineering [9], and its implementation with empirical logic can be found in more detail in the doctoral thesis of the author [2, pp. 183-200]. The control element labeled "amplifier" in Fig. 1 is to be replaced and examined below by suitably dimensioned controllers of the PI, PID and EL^2 types.

Fig. 1: Speed control of a DC drive³

For the structural analysis and the derivation of the equations that describe the electrical behavior of the motor, the mechanical movement of the motor armature with load, and the transfer behavior of the converter circuit and the control amplifier, please refer to the relevant sections in the book of Otto Föllinger [9, pp. 90-93]. The results of a functional analysis are reflected in the structural picture of the control circuit shown in Fig. 2.

² “EL” here refers to an empirical logic control unit.

³ Image reproduction courtesy of VDE-Verlag.

Fig. 2: Structural diagram of the DC drive speed control loop

3.1. Determining the control engineering categories

Fig. 3: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Controlled variable deviation $e(t)$ ” [volt]

Fig. 4: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Change of the controlled variable deviation $c(t)$ ” [volt/sec]

Fig. 5: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Acceleration of the controlled variable deviation $a(t)$ ” [volt/sec²]

Fig. 6: Bound categories belonging to reference magnitude “Correcting variable $u(t)$ ” [volt]

The relevant reference magnitudes for the still to be determined bound categories of an EL controller can be read from Fig. 2, as follows:⁴

$e(t)$ = Deviation u_D of the feedback variable u_1 , which is proportional to the controlled variable ω , from the reference variable u_S at the controller input

$u(t)$ = Correcting variable u_C at the controller output

In addition, it makes sense to calculate the change (first derivative) of the controlled variable deviation to be used as a further reference magnitude:

$$c(t_{n+1}) = \frac{e(t_{n+1}) - e(t_n)}{\Delta t}$$

Δt denotes the duration between two consecutive sampling times t_n and t_{n+1} .

⁴ The neutral designations ($e(t)$ instead of $u_D(t)$ and $u(t)$ instead of $u_C(t)$) correspond to the nomenclature customary in control engineering.

Category name	Validity function			
	Operator	Arguments		
		Reference magnitude	Validity threshold/limitation	Fuzziness
<i>Controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive</i>	<i>e_THRESHOLD</i>	<i>e(t)</i>	0	0.37
<i>Controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative</i>	<i>e_LIMITATION</i>	<i>e(t)</i>	0	0.37
<i>Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive</i>	<i>e_THRESHOLD</i>	<i>c(t)</i>	0	8
<i>Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative</i>	<i>e_LIMITATION</i>	<i>c(t)</i>	0	8
<i>Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive</i>	<i>e_THRESHOLD</i>	<i>a(t)</i>	0	300
<i>Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative</i>	<i>e_LIMITATION</i>	<i>a(t)</i>	0	300
<i>Correcting_variable_is_positive</i>	<i>e_THRESHOLD</i>	<i>u(t)</i>	0	2.6
<i>Correcting_variable_is_negative</i>	<i>e_LIMITATION</i>	<i>u(t)</i>	0	2.6

Tab. 1: Validity functions of the categories and their arguments

The fact that, after a closer look at the inner loop of the structural diagram of **Fig. 2**, the DC drive turns out to be a controlled section with three time constants⁵ suggests that stabilization of the control loop cannot be achieved without taking into account the acceleration (second derivative) of the controlled variable deviation $e(t)$ as a fourth reference magnitude for the design of the empirical logic controller:

$$a(t_{n+1}) = \frac{c(t_{n+1}) - c(t_n)}{\Delta t}$$

The bound categories shown graphically in **Fig. 3**, **Fig. 4**, **Fig. 5** and **Fig. 6** are derived from the reference magnitudes mentioned above.⁶

Among the available validity functions, the threshold function $e_THRESHOLD$ and the limitation function $e_LIMITATION$ are suitable for representing these categories. **Tab. 1** shows these with the corresponding arguments assigned. The rationale for the specific selection of the fuzziness parameter values is given below.

3.2. The empirical logic rules of the DC drive speed control

The only two rules required for controlling a DC drive with the help of empirical logic can be expressed in such a way that they correspond to intuition and do not require any additional explanation (**Tab. 2**):

Rule 1	IF	the controlled variable deviation is positive
	OR	the change of the controlled variable deviation is positive
	OR	the acceleration of the controlled variable deviation is positive,
	THEN	increase the correcting variable.
Rule 2	IF	the controlled variable deviation is negative
	OR	the change of the controlled variable deviation is negative
	OR	the acceleration of the controlled variable deviation is negative,
	THEN	decrease the correcting variable.

Tab. 2: The empirical logic rules of the DC drive control

For the rule conclusions, the inverse validity functions $e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE$ and $e_LIMITATION_INVERSE$ are used, such that:

⁵ The corresponding analysis with an equivalent transformation of the structural diagram can be found in Föllinger [9, pp. 90-93].

⁶ For the sake of simplicity, the reference values are denoted as dimensionless.

$$\text{Increase_the_correcting_variable} := \begin{cases} \mathbb{V} & \rightarrow [0, 1] \\ u & \mapsto e_THRESHOLD_INVERSE(u, -5, 5, 0, 2.6) \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Decrease_the_correcting_variable} := \begin{cases} \mathbb{V} & \rightarrow [0, 1] \\ u & \mapsto e_LIMITATION_INVERSE(u, -5, 5, 0, 2.6) \end{cases}$$

Fig. 7 shows the translation of the rules presented in Tab. 2 into Maple code.

```
#
# 1. Rule:
#
premiseRule1 := e_OR(Controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive(e),
                    Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive(c),
                    Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_positive(a)
                    );
if premiseRule1 > e_UNKNOWN() then
    conclusionRule1 := e_VALIDATE(premiseRule1, Correcting_variable_is_positive(u));
    next_u1 := Increase_the_correcting_variable(conclusionRule1);
else
    next_u1 := NULL;
end if;
#
# 2. Rule:
#
premiseRule2 := e_OR(Controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative(e),
                    Change_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative(c),
                    Acceleration_of_the_controlled_variable_deviation_is_negative(a)
                    );
if premiseRule2 > e_UNKNOWN() then
    conclusionRule2 := e_VALIDATE(premiseRule2, Correcting_variable_is_negative(u));
    next_u2 := Decrease_the_correcting_variable(conclusionRule2);
else
    next_u2 := NULL;
end if;
```

Fig. 7: The empirical logic rules translated into Maple code

In principle, it is possible that the premises of both rules are met simultaneously, resulting in competing new settings for the manipulated variables $next_u1$ and $next_u2$. In this case, it must be clarified which new setting $next_u$ of the correcting variable u should be calculated from the two proposed values $next_u1$ and $next_u2$. The simplest method to do so is to calculate the arithmetic mean (Fig. 8):

```
next_u_list := [next_u1, next_u2];
n := nops(next_u_list);
if n > 0 then
    u := sum(next_u_list[i], i = 1..n)/n;
end if;
```

Fig. 8: Resolving a rule conflict

3.3. Simulating the speed control using empirical logic

To test the EL controller, the author used a simulation kit developed with Maple, which allows a comparison of its dynamic behavior with that of a PI and PID type controller. The design of a PI or PID controller for the DC drive from Fig. 1 can be found in Föllinger [9, pp. 185-188]. There are synthesis methods or proven rules of thumb for the selection and dimensioning of conventional controller types. These are not available for the design of an EL controller due to its non-linearity, so that simulation experiments are required to determine the controller parameters. The term “controller parameters” here refers to the determination of the *fuzziness* parameters of the validity functions that describe the bound categories of the DC drive speed control system (Fig. 3, Fig. 4, Fig. 5, Fig. 6). However, it is possible to take advantage of the effect of different degrees of fuzziness of the categories based on the results of the rule applications. It is observed that the rules react

“sensitively” to categories with low fuzziness and “softly” to categories with greater fuzziness. As a "rule of thumb", the following orientation aid can be useful:

1. Category fuzziness of the reference magnitude at the controller input $\approx \frac{1}{4}$ value range
2. Category fuzziness of the reference magnitude at the controller output $\approx \frac{1}{2}$ value range

When using a control system developed with empirical logic for the first time, the value range can sometimes be difficult to assess. However, for the DC drive speed control, it is feasible to take over the value ranges from the simulations with a PI or PID controller and then to experimentally readjust the fuzziness parameters calculated with it if necessary. A PI controller with a loop gain of $V = 50$, for example, yielded the values listed in **Tab. 3**.

Reference magnitude	Value range			Assigned fuzziness
	Min	Max	Max - Min	
Controlled variable deviation $e(t)$	-0.47	1.0	1.47	0.37
Change of the controlled variable deviation $c(t)$	-21.57	10.39	31.96	8
Acceleration of the controlled variable deviation $a(t)$	-702.3	470.21	1172.51	300
Correcting variable $u(t)$	-1.56	3.68	5.24	2.6

Tab. 3: Determination of the EL controller parameters

With these parameter settings, the reference and disturbance step responses of the DC drive operated with an EL controller are shown in **Fig. 9** and **Fig. 10**.

Fig. 9: Reference step response of the EL controller

Fig. 10: Disturbance step response of the EL controller

3.4. Comparing the simulation results

The graphs of the step responses shown in Fig. 9 and Fig. 10 use different scales in order to be able to display the curves as precisely as possible. However, a uniform scale is required for a direct comparison of the different controller types. In addition, a loop gain V that is as favorable as possible should be selected regarding the stabilization behavior of the respective controller type. As shown in Fig. 11, the EL controller responds to a reference step change faster than the PI controller but slower than the PID controller. After a disturbance step, the controlled variable deviates only slightly from the setpoint – like the PID controller – and reaches the steady-state condition even faster (see Fig. 12).

Fig. 11: Comparing the reference step responses

Fig. 12: Comparing the disturbance step responses

4 Summary

It can be stated that the example of a DC drive described here demonstrates the suitability of empirical logic for use in control technology. Due to the non-linear transfer behavior of an EL controller, however, there is still no practically proven synthesis method with which the control behavior could be optimized for given boundary conditions. However, this disadvantage becomes less important with the “rule of thumb” presented above for determining the fuzziness parameters of the bound categories. The simulation experiments also have shown that the sensitivity to suboptimal parameter settings is low. Special mention should be made of the clear superiority over fuzzy control technology, as EL controllers require very few and easily defined rules.

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